

UZBEKISTAN'S STRATEGY FOR TRANSITION TO "GREEN ECONOMY": EXISTING PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTIVE OPPORTUNITIES

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***Abstract.** In this article, the concept of green economy and its importance will be considered. In which countries are promoting the green economy, as well as the introduction of the concept of the green economy to Uzbekistan, its problems and promising opportunities are shown separately. The article examines the interdependence of ecology and economy, the impact and results of economic activity on the environment. The transition to a “green economy” and its advantages and strategies are considered in order to significantly reduce environmental risks and degradation of nature caused by the country’s economy and production.*

***Keywords:** green economy, green development, ecological economy, resources, global goals, P4G platform, UN Trust Fund, ecology, anomalous nature, atmospheric pollution, Aral Sea, UNICEF, Celsius scale, concepts.*

Introduction. Currently, many countries around the world are pursuing a “green” economy as a guarantee of stable development. Numerous scholars around the globe emphasize the necessity of transitioning to a “green” economy due to ecological issues like climate change, continuous population growth—social problems, and increasing unemployment—economic problems, all stemming from ongoing crises in various sectors of the economy.

The sharp changes in the climate and anomalous natural phenomena present new ecological threats, leading to instability and unpredictable anxieties for society and the environment. The measures and concepts adopted by all countries and international organizations to achieve sustainable development, which reflects global interests, underline the necessity of transitioning to a “green” economy. This transition is considered one of the most important tools for achieving sustainable growth.

This concept has also reached Uzbekistan; the notion of a green economy emerged as a direction within economic sciences in the late last century. This economy is an integral part of the natural environment and represents one of its dimensions. The concept of a green economy encompasses ideas from various fields of economic sciences and philosophy, including ecological economics related to nature and society, environmental economics, resource-based economics, and economic aspects of population development associated with green policies.

The green economy is an economic system whose main goal is to develop all sectors of the economy while preserving the ecology of our planet. Thus, the green economy refers to a new direction of economic activity based on the sustainable management of resources essential for human life and health, while also integrating production and service sectors in relation to the environment and ecology.

Our President, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, delivered a speech at the second international summit “Green Growth and Global Goals Partnership – 2030” (P4G) held in the Republic of Korea. In his speech, the head of state emphasized: “Today, we must not be indifferent to the warning signals that nature is sending us. Unfortunately, climate change is intensifying. In Central Asia, where we live, the average annual temperature has increased by about one degree over the past 30 years. The shrinking of the basin of the main rivers in our region and the decline in biodiversity are causing serious concern. The increase in gases that raise evaporation levels and widespread atmospheric pollution are exacerbating these problems. There is no doubt that today, achieving the goals related to ‘green development’ requires countries to act more actively and effectively. We have no other choice”.

Additionally, the head of state emphasized the need to unite the efforts of the entire international community to adopt effective decisions that serve “green” and sustainable development. Overcoming the global consequences of the Aral Sea disaster was identified as one of the priority tasks. In this regard, the President expressed gratitude to all international partners for their full support of the special resolution adopted by the UN General Assembly, declaring the Aral Sea region an area for ecological innovations and technologies. He proposed to actively continue work in this direction within the framework of specially established UN Trust Funds, the Global Institute for Green Growth, the “P4G” partnership platform, and other international institutions.

Concerns were raised regarding the impact of climate change, gases that increase evaporation levels, and atmospheric pollution, which are leading to the decline of transboundary river flows and biodiversity in our region.

The “P4G” partnership platform aims to contribute to green and inclusive growth in low- and middle-income countries by helping early-stage businesses prepare for investment and supporting national climate adaptation in food, water, and energy systems. It provides grants and technical assistance to prepare for investments in green growth and serves as a platform that can help improve systems in partner countries.

Literature Review. Economic and ecological crises typically arise from the same sources and significantly influence each other. This is because the current economic model seeks short-term profit without considering the consequences for the environment and society, neglecting ecosystems.

In the context of globalization, a new trend towards a “green” economy has emerged in response to the challenges facing the economy due to failures in market economics. This new economic thinking focuses on searching for strategies to address various crises that have hindered the development of global society in recent years. For instance, the effects of climate change, food shortages, the economic and financial crises caused by the pandemic, and the sluggishness in combating poverty are significant factors in defining the concept of “green” economy within the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP).

The “green” economy concept represents a model that aims to improve the health and social equity of populations while significantly reducing harmful impacts on the environment and decreasing ecological scarcity.

Thus, the “green” economy can be seen in its simplest form as a low-carbon, resource-efficient, and socially inclusive model of the economy. The goal of the “green” economy concept is to ensure sustainable economic growth and increase investment activity while improving

environmental protection and the quality of social integration. To achieve this goal, it is essential to widely direct both public and private investments towards the ecological and social factors of sustainable development.

While the “green” economy concept does not entirely fulfill the objectives of sustainable development, it is considered an economically based model for achieving sustainability.

In 1992, during the United Nations conference in Rio de Janeiro, the international community adopted the “Agenda 21” which established global cooperation in pursuit of high-level sustainable development interests.

The main task of the “green” economy is to transform production and consumption processes in accordance with ecological standards.

The “green” economy concept encompasses the following five principles:

Creating and ensuring effective utilization of human well-being.

Ensuring economic and social equality among people.

Protecting and restoring nature.

Supporting the transition to low-carbon, resource-efficient, diverse, and resilient forms of consumption and production.

Establishing a financial system that aligns with societal interests to ensure human well-being and sustainability.

Additionally, the “green” economy relies on three main strategies:

Reducing carbon emissions.

Increasing energy efficiency.

Making prudent use of natural resources.

In this context, it is essential to prevent the loss of biodiversity and ecosystem services, supporting the implementation of these strategies through investments at both public and private levels. Political and regulatory reforms are necessary in this regard. Therefore, preserving, strengthening, and, when necessary, rebuilding natural capital is of significant importance as economic and public interests linked to the development of certain sectors of society.

In most interpretations of the “green” economy, the interconnection between ecosystems, the economy, human well-being, and related forms of capital is recognized. The United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) defines the “green” economy as a means to enhance human well-being and social equality while significantly reducing negative impacts on the environment and the risk of ecological decline.

The relevance and necessity of transitioning to a “green economy” are determined by the following factors:

The need to implement technological modernization in the economy to reduce the negative consequences of environmental pollution and the depletion of natural resources.

Increasing the competitiveness of the economy by reducing its dependence on hydrocarbon raw materials and their share in final product value.

Applying green innovations that allow for the renewal of high-tech sectors, which have a large multiplicative effect.

Reducing dependence on hydrocarbons during the transition to a low-carbon economy.

As mentioned above, the initiative for developing a “green economy” was proposed by UNEP in 2008 and is based on the following general principles:

Assessing environmental problems at national and international levels and prioritizing them on the agenda.

Ensuring employment for the population by creating “green” jobs and developing relevant measures.

Utilizing market mechanisms to achieve sustainable development.

The concept of a “green economy” is based on the following axioms: a) it is impossible to infinitely expand the scope of impact in a limited environment; b) there is no possibility of satisfying growing needs in the context of limited resources; c) everything on Earth is interconnected.

UNEP experts categorize the sectors of the “green economy” into two groups: a) sectors related to “natural capital,” such as raw material extraction, agriculture, fishing, forestry, and water resource management; b) sectors related to “energy and resource efficiency,” including energy, the recycling industry, machinery, transportation, and construction.

Some experts emphasize the need to apply the Clark-Fisher model when identifying the directions for developing the “green economy.” The Clark-Fisher model theoretically justifies the significance of the extraction, processing, and service sectors in creating jobs during the stages of economic development. This model is supplemented by innovative sectors characteristic of the economy, such as “green” services related to the sectors proposed by UN experts in the “green economy,” including high-capacity production, tourism, urban management, waste disposal, education, scientific research, and financial services.

Research Methodology. The necessity for transitioning to a “green economy” in Uzbekistan is explained by the fact that a significant portion of the energy consumed in the national economy is produced from non-renewable natural resources, the limited reserves of these resources, and the environmental issues exacerbated by rapid industrial development, such as pollution, water scarcity, and the drying of the Aral Sea. The sustainable development of Uzbekistan’s economy requires the consideration of internal and global processes and problems in the long-term strategy for structural changes. According to the World Meteorological Organization of the UN, the global annual average air temperature has increased by 1°C from the level recorded in 1880. In Uzbekistan, the average annual air temperature for the same period has risen by 1.6°C (from 13.2°C to 14.8°C). The rate of increase in the average air temperature in our country is higher than the average rate observed globally. Climate warming negatively impacts ecosystems and has led to a deterioration of the ecological situation in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, as well as in the provinces of Khorezm, Bukhara, Navoi, Kashkadarya, Samarkand, and Surkhandarya. For this reason, to respond comprehensively to the growing global threats related to climate change, the Paris Agreement was adopted at the 21st session of the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) conference held in the capital of France on December 12, 2015.

This agreement came into force on November 4, 2016, and was implemented starting in 2020. Currently, 180 out of the 197 countries that signed the Paris Agreement have ratified the document. Countries that have not ratified the agreement hold an observer status and face restrictions in accessing climate financing. The goal of the Paris Agreement is to limit global warming to 2°C above the average temperature during the industrial development period, compared to the year 2020, and to strive to limit the temperature increase to 1.5°C. By 2050, it requires a reduction of global greenhouse gas emissions by 40-70%, and by 2100, it aims to

achieve net-zero or negative emissions. The agreement places an obligation on developed countries to support developing countries in their efforts to mitigate and adapt to climate change.

In 2020, it was decided to increase financial assistance to \$100 billion, taking into account the needs and priorities of developing countries. Currently, a fund is financing 35 projects with a total value of \$1.5 billion. Among these projects is the issue of financing the "Climate Change Adaptation and Mitigation Program for the Aral Sea Basin" in cooperation with the World Bank for Uzbekistan and Tajikistan. On April 19, 2017, Uzbekistan signed the "Uzbekistan-Paris" Agreement at the UN Headquarters in New York. Uzbekistan's active participation in the Paris Agreement provides the following benefits for our country:

Attracting climate financing resources (mainly grants) in the implementation of State programs for energy efficiency and energy conservation, improving the management of land and water resources, combating negative consequences (the Aral Sea disaster, desertification, drought), and other opportunities (Article 9, Paragraph 7);

Participation in the Paris Agreement serves as an indicator for attracting investment resources and obtaining loans from international financial institutions and donor countries;

Utilizing new technologies for mitigating climate change and fostering collaboration in the field of innovative technologies (Article 10);

Cooperation in the area of climate change adaptation enables the country to implement adaptation measures to enhance resilience and reduce vulnerability (national interests). This is considered crucial from the perspective of addressing the Aral Sea disaster.

In cases where evidence of damage caused by climate change is presented, the adverse effects of climate change will be addressed by donors. The insufficient energy efficiency of the national economy, the irrational use of natural resources, the slow pace of technology renewal, and the lack of active participation from small businesses in implementing innovative solutions for developing a "green" economy hinder achieving the priority goals of sustainable development in the national economy. The absence of a long-term strategy in this area has so far prevented the implementation of systematic measures for the introduction of "green" technologies and the transition to a "green" economy.

A long-term comprehensive set of measures for developing a "green economy" in Uzbekistan has been developed in alignment with the UN initiative and the sustainable development goals set for 2030. Since 2015, Uzbekistan has expressed its support for the UN's sustainable development program, which includes 17 goals and 169 tasks aimed at sustainable development, and has stated its intention to carry out comprehensive work in various fields of sustainable development:

Ensuring access for all to affordable, reliable, sustainable, and modern energy sources, with the goal of significantly increasing the share of renewable energy sources in global energy balance by 2030;

Doubling the rate of energy efficiency improvements; expanding infrastructure and modernizing technologies for the provision of modern and sustainable energy (Goal 7);

Integrating measures to counteract climate change into national policies, strategies, and planning, improving awareness and capacity to prevent the impacts of climate change, adapt to it, and provide early warning of hazardous climate events (Goal 13);

Protecting and restoring terrestrial ecosystems, promoting the sustainable use of forests, combating desertification, halting and reversing land degradation, and ensuring sustainable land use practices.

Within the framework of the UN Sustainable Development Program, support for sustainable and inclusive economic growth, full and productive employment, and decent work for all (Goal 8) is emphasized, along with the establishment of resilient infrastructure, fostering inclusive and sustainable industrialization, and promoting innovation (Goal 9).

The adoption of the Development Strategy for 2017-2021 reaffirmed that the development of a "green economy" is one of the factors for ensuring sustainable economic growth in our country.

In order to consistently implement the tasks outlined in the Development Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021, including fulfilling the obligations of the Paris Agreement, on October 4, 2019, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan approved the Resolution PR-4477 on "Approval of the Strategy for Transitioning the Republic of Uzbekistan to a 'Green' Economy for 2019-2030".

The aim of the strategy is to achieve stable economic growth that ensures social development, reduces greenhouse gas emissions, and guarantees climate and ecological sustainability by integrating the principles of a "green" economy into ongoing structural reforms in the country. To achieve the goals of the strategy, it is necessary to implement the following key tasks:

Increasing energy efficiency in the economy and promoting the rational use of natural resources through technological modernization and the development of financial mechanisms;

Introducing "green" criteria based on advanced international standards into the priority areas of state investments and expenditures;

Supporting the implementation of pilot projects in the direction of transitioning to a "green" economy through the development of government incentives, the promotion of public-private partnerships, and the activation of cooperation with international financial institutions;

Developing a training and retraining system for specialists related to the labor market in the "green" economy by encouraging investments in education and enhancing cooperation with leading foreign educational institutions and research centers;

Taking measures to mitigate the negative impacts of the ecological crisis in the Aral Sea region;

Strengthening international cooperation in the field of "green" economy, including the establishment of bilateral and multilateral agreements.

In Uzbekistan, the long-term strategy for transitioning to a "green" economy is based on the following principles:

Compliance with national goals and objectives in the field of sustainable development;

Rational use of resources, sustainable consumption, and production;

Incorporation of ecological and social criteria into the economic accounting system;

Priority for applying "green" tools and approaches to achieve socio-economic development goals;

Increasing competitiveness in key sectors of the national economy and improving performance indicators, creating "green" jobs, and enhancing the well-being of the population to achieve existing macroeconomic goals;

Ensuring the investment attractiveness of measures for the effective use of resources. Achieving the aforementioned goals and objectives will increase the competitiveness of the national economy and improve the quality of life of the population while enabling a transition to a sustainable development path based on a "green" economy.

Analysis and Discussion of Results. From the current changes and the literature review, we can analyze that, first and foremost, it is essential to sustainably increase the production of material goods to meet the needs of the population and enhance their well-being, living standards, and quality of life without harming ecology and the environment.

Secondly, energy resources are needed for production and economic development. It is necessary to increase these resources through renewable energy sources, replace public transport with electric-powered vehicles, and construct energy-efficient buildings.

Thirdly, it is essential to focus on the issue of producing eco-friendly products through the creation of environmentally clean technologies that do not emit harmful gases into the atmosphere and preserve the environment.

Fourthly, given that all resources in nature are limited while human needs are infinite, it is crucial to implement measures that expand production without depleting natural resources in order to ensure their compatibility.

Fifthly, addressing the constantly growing needs of the population involves significant consideration of how much to produce, how to produce, and for whom to produce, all while safeguarding the environment.

Conclusion and Recommendations

In conclusion, it can be said that the green economy must ensure the harmonious and sustainable development of humans, nature, and the economy. One should not lose something while trying to achieve another. For example, when constructing a house, trees should not be ruthlessly cut down; increasing technologies should not come at the expense of filling the atmosphere with toxic gases, and so on. Achieving sustainable development is one of the pressing global issues today.

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